

Constraining CMIP6 simulations for the Atlantic Water in the Arctic using an AMOC-SST index

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2 ABSTRACT

3 The Atlantic Water plays a key role regarding the future changes in the Arctic Ocean. It contributes
4 to the Atlantification by transporting salt and heat within the Arctic Ocean basins. Many studies
5 also attribute the amplified Arctic Ocean warming to an increase in poleward ocean heat transport
6 by warming currents or increasing strength of ocean currents. Global models are needed to
7 predict reliable and consistent trends of heat transport as large scale processes are at play. They
8 are however too coarse to resolve key ocean processes and deal with the complex interplay
9 between ocean dynamics and bathymetry of the Arctic region. Here we propose to construct a
10 sub-ensemble of simulations based on 235 historical simulations from 12 CMIP6 models that
11 best represents the downstream drivers of Atlantic warming. We select the model ensemble
12 members showing the closest agreement with observed surface temperature variability over
13 1960-1990 in the subpolar gyre (SPG). More specifically we use a recent index that links the
14 surface temperature in the SPG to the Atlantic Overturning Meridional Circulation (AMOC): the
15 AMOC-SST index. The subsampled ensemble shows a better correlation with the observed
16 AMOC-SST index over the last 35 years of the historical period (1980-2014). It also displays over
17 the latter period a reduced error and better correlation for the Atlantic Water core temperature
18 and depth in the Eurasian Arctic Ocean, when compared to reanalysis and observations. Overall,
19 the AMOC-SST index based selection leads to a systematic improvement of the representation
20 of the Atlantic Water layer in the Eurasian Arctic region, suggesting a clear connection between
21 the Arctic Ocean and the surface temperature in the subpolar region, and by extension, possibly
22 the AMOC.

23 **Keywords:** Arctic, Atlantic Water, Subpolar Gyre, AMOC

1 INTRODUCTION

24 There is an urgent need to reduce the uncertainty in predicted Arctic Ocean climate change: it is changing
25 more rapidly than the rest of the globe due to the "Arctic amplification" phenomenon (Rantanen et al.,
26 2022; Serreze and Barry, 2011), and those fast changes have global repercussions (Goosse et al., 2018;
27 Pithan and Mauritsen, 2014). Over the past decades, both models and observations have shown a positive

28 trend in the northward transport of ocean heat to the Arctic Ocean by Atlantic inflows, which has strongly
29 affected the Arctic climate (Årthun et al., 2012; Barton et al., 2018; Wang et al., 2020; Tsubouchi et al.,
30 2021; Polyakov et al., 2023; Hansen et al., 2023).

31 The primary water mass at the Arctic intermediate depth, the Atlantic Water (AW), plays a key role in
32 the heat budget of the Arctic Ocean (Shu et al., 2019). Research indicates that one of the main reasons for
33 increased heat transport to the Arctic Ocean is the warmer temperatures of the AW transported northward
34 mostly through the Barents Sea but also through Fram Strait (Koenigk and Brodeau, 2014; Oldenburg
35 et al., 2018). In more details (see Supplementary Fig. S1), it originates in the North Atlantic, and warm and
36 saline AW flows into the Nordic Seas (Orvik and Niiler, 2002), with a portion entering the Barents Sea
37 before descending into the intermediate and deeper layers of the Arctic Ocean (Maslowski et al., 2004).
38 The remaining AW approaches the Fram Strait, where it splits into two pathways: one portion enters the
39 Arctic Ocean, contributing to the warm AW layer, while the other recirculates within the Fram Strait as
40 part of the West Spitsbergen Current and eventually joins the southward-flowing East Greenland Current
41 (Hattermann et al., 2016). A recent warming trend in the AW layer in the Arctic Ocean has been observed
42 (Polyakov et al., 2012).

43 The climate models in the Coupled Model Intercomparison Project (CMIP) still underestimate the ocean
44 heat transport to the Arctic (Winkelbauer et al., 2024) and that could lead to an underestimation of Arctic
45 region changes. They are struggling with the particular configuration of this area that displays complex
46 bathymetry (Heuzé et al., 2023) and dynamical processes that usually require higher resolution than the
47 one typically adopted by the last CMIP (Wang et al., 2024). The models tend to represent the AW layer
48 as too thick and too deep, with a large spread of both too warm and too cold temperature compared to
49 observations (Heuzé et al., 2023; Khosravi et al., 2022).

50 The climate models also diverge in their projections of Arctic climate change (Mulwijk et al., 2023), in
51 particular at intermediate depth (Langehaug et al., 2023). Projected weakening of the AMOC (IPCC, 2023;
52 Weijer et al., 2020) is expected to affect the exchanges with the Arctic, but climate models demonstrate
53 strong differences in the projections for that part of the AMOC that involves the exchanges with the Arctic
54 through ocean heat transport (Sgubin et al., 2017; Madonna and Sandø, 2022). In particular, (Pan et al.,
55 2023) showed that the discrepancies between the model projections are strongly related to the simulated
56 poleward ocean heat transport (OHT) from the North Atlantic, which is very different depending on the
57 ocean component used by the climate model. The large group of NEMO (Nucleus for European Modelling
58 of the Ocean) based climate models tend to project larger increases in OHT thus simulating stronger and
59 more rapid Arctic climate change compared to other climate models. In the most recent version of the
60 CMIP project (CMIP6), OHT in the models showed less inter-model spread and mean values closer to
61 observations compared to CMIP5 models (Madonna and Sandø, 2022).

62 Applying external constraints to the ensemble of simulations may help to reduce uncertainties in the
63 future projections and model biases regarding OHT. Through CMIP6, an impressive amount of coordinated
64 and thus comparable simulations were performed across model systems. This allows us to explore statistical
65 sampling methods using observed metrics to improve the skill for Arctic prediction beyond the model
66 mean. Moreover, model and model member (simulation) selection is more and more explored in the context
67 of data assimilation (Ruiz et al., 2022; Le Bras et al., 2024) or emergent constraints (Tokarska et al., 2020;
68 Ribes et al., 2021; Docquier and Koenigk, 2021; Langehaug et al., 2023). Selecting individual simulations
69 from a model using observations provides new insights (Bonnet et al., 2021) and should be considered
70 for models showing huge spread in their ensemble (Deser et al., 2020; Mankin et al., 2020; Meccia et al.,

71 2023). We propose here to constrain a part of the CMIP6 ensemble of simulations by selecting specific
72 model ensemble members to reduce the uncertainty in the representation of the subsurface Arctic Ocean.

73 In the selection method, we investigate the connection between the subpolar North Atlantic Ocean and
74 the Arctic Ocean. The gyre circulation in the northern North Atlantic and its associated heat transport are
75 indeed recognized as significant factors in the warming of the Arctic Ocean (e.g., Jungclaus et al. (2014);
76 Oldenburg et al. (2018); van der Linden et al. (2019)). On decadal time-scale, (Fan et al., 2023) showed that
77 subpolar gyre (SPG) signal provides predictability for Nordic Seas salinity and temperature. It was also
78 found in observations (Årthun et al., 2017) and pacemaker experiments using climate models (Drews et al.,
79 2024) that surface temperature anomalies in the Northern Atlantic have predictive potential for northern
80 climate.

81 On a longer time scale, some links can be found between the changes in ocean heat transport towards
82 the Arctic and the variability of the Atlantic Meridional Overturning Circulation (AMOC). A proposed
83 signature of a weakened AMOC is a cooling of the sea surface temperature (SST) of the SPG, due to
84 a result of a reduced heat transport towards northern latitudes (Caesar et al., 2018; Gervais et al., 2018;
85 Saba et al., 2016). Other studies suggest that the warming hole during the past century is unlikely due to
86 a slowdown of the AMOC and is rather a consequence of enhanced northward heat transport out of the
87 region (Keil et al., 2020; He et al., 2022), explained by a trend toward a more frequent positive phase of the
88 North Atlantic Oscillation (Fan et al., 2023). Nevertheless, under strong global warming and weakened
89 AMOC, (Oldenburg et al., 2018) found in CMIP5 models an increased Arctic OHT as strengthened gyre
90 circulations advect warmed surface waters. Heat loss to the atmosphere is reduced, leaving more heat
91 in the subpolar ocean that contributes to enhanced ocean heat transport to the Arctic Ocean (Nummelin
92 et al., 2017). Finally, (Weijer et al., 2022) provides some evidence that AMOC may influence the Arctic
93 heat budget through its impact on poleward heat transport as climate models simulating future scenarios
94 almost unanimously project a decrease in the strength of the AMOC and often an increase in OHT into the
95 Arctic (Hwang et al., 2011). Furthermore, as heat loss from the North Atlantic declines, it can contribute
96 to the weakening of the AMOC (Garuba and Klinger, 2016; Gregory et al., 2016; Couldrey et al., 2021).
97 We explore these links between AMOC and the Arctic Ocean in this study, using for our selection a
98 reconstructed AMOC index based on the anomaly between the SST in the SPG and the global SST (Caesar
99 et al., 2018). The selected members are evaluated in their ability to represent the Atlantic Water layer in the
100 Eurasian Arctic region.

101 In the section 2 we describe our datasets, the selection method and the evaluation tools of the selected
102 subset in the Arctic. The section 3 provides the results obtained for the selected model ensemble members.
103 Finally a discussion and a conclusion summarise the study and open for perspectives.

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

104 2.1 Data

105 2.1.1 CMIP6 models

106 We use historical simulations under transient forcing that are available for the period 1850-2014 on the
107 CMIP6 ESGF nodes Eyring et al. (2016). The selection of the members is done over the period 1960-1990
108 and evaluation in the Arctic over the period 1980-2014.

109 We have included the models that displayed at least around 20 members, so a total of 235 members
110 constitutes the working data-base. Models are listed and described in table 1.

No.	Model	Nb of members	Ocean grid resolution	Nb of levels	Ocean	Institution
1	ACCESS-ESM1-5 (Ziehn et al., 2020)	20	360x300	50	MOM5.1	CSIRO-ARCCSS, Australia
2	CanESM5* (Swart et al., 2019)	20	360x291	45	NEMO3.4	CCCa, ECC, Canada
3	CNRM-CM6-1* (Voldoire et al., 2019)	20	362x294	75	NEMO3.6	CNRM, CERFACS, France
4	EC-Earth3* (Döscher et al., 2022)	20	362x292	75	NEMO3.6	EC-Earth-Consortium France
5	E3SM-2-0 (Golaz et al., 2022)	18	30/60 km (unstructured)	60	MPAS-Ocean	LLNL, ANL, BNL, LANL, LBNL, ORNL, PNNL, SNL, USA
6	GISS-E2-1-G (Kelley et al., 2020)	20	360x180	40	GISS Ocean v1	Goddard Institute for Space Studies, USA
7	HadGEM3-GC31-LL* (Andrews et al., 2020)	20	360x330	75	NEMO-HG3-GO6	Met Office Hadley Centre, UK
8	IPSL-CM6A-LR* (Boucher et al., 2020)	20	360x332	75	NEMO-OPA	Institut Pierre Simon Laplace, France
9	MPI-ESM1-2-LR (Mauritsen et al., 2019)	20	256x220	40	MPIOM1.63	Max Planck Institute for Meteorology, Germany
10	MIROC6 (Tatebe et al., 2019)	20	360x256	63	COCO4.9	JAMSTEC, AORI, NIES, RIKEN, Japan
11	NorCPM1 (Bethke et al., 2021)	20	320x384	53	MICOM1.1	NorESM Climate modeling Consortium, Norway
12	UKESM1-0-LL* (Sellar et al., 2019)	17	360x330	75	NEMO-HG3-GO6	Met Office Hadley Centre, UK

Table 1. Description of the CMIP6 models used in the study, including their research centers for development (institutions), number of members that are included, and the name and resolution of their ocean components. Models with * have NEMO as ocean component.

111 2.1.2 Observations and Reanalysis

112 HadISST

113 Sea Surface Temperature (SST) data are sourced from the HadISST (Hadley Centre Global Sea
114 Ice and Sea Surface Temperature) dataset developed by Rayner et al. (2003). This dataset combines
115 global monthly SST and sea ice concentration fields, covering the period from 1871 to the present.
116 HadISST employs reduced space optimal interpolation for SST data collected from the Marine
117 Data Bank (mainly ship routes) and ICOADS (International Comprehensive Ocean–Atmosphere
118 Data Set) up to 1981, followed by a blend of in-situ and adjusted satellite SSTs from 1982 onwards.

119 EN4

120 EN4 (Good et al., 2013) is a global ocean subsurface temperature and salinity dataset covering
121 1900 to the present. It provides two main data products: (1) a database of quality-controlled *in*
122 *situ* profiles, and (2) spatially complete analyses with a $1^\circ \times 1^\circ$ horizontal resolution and 42 depth
123 levels from 83°S to 90°N . Data sources include Argo (2000), ASBO (Arctic Synoptic Basinwide
124 Oceanography), GTSP (Global Temperature and Salinity Profile Program), and WOD13 (World
125 Ocean Database). Analyses include observation weights and standard error information. Due to

126 sparse observations in some regions, EN4 defaults to a 1970-2000 climatology. To correspond to
127 the CMIP historical period delimitation, we will use EN4 product over 1970-2014.

128 **ORAS5**

129 The Ocean Reanalysis System 5 (ORAS5) reanalysis dataset provides global ocean and sea-ice
130 reanalysis monthly mean data prepared by the European Centre for ECMWF OCEAN5 ocean
131 analysis-reanalysis system (Copernicus, 2021). OCEAN5 (Zuo et al., 2019) uses the NEMO
132 ocean model and assimilates sub-surface temperature, salinity, sea-ice concentration and sea-level
133 anomalies. The consolidated product uses reanalysis atmospheric forcing (ERA-40 until 1978
134 and ERA-Interim from 1979) and re-processed observations. The ORAS5 dataset is produced by
135 ECMWF and funded by the Copernicus Climate Change Service. To correspond to the CMIP
136 historical period delimitation, we will use ORAS5 reanalysis over 1979-2014.

137 **2.2 Method**

138 2.2.1 AWCT and AWCD Definition

139 In this study, we define the Atlantic Water Core Temperature (AWCT) as the maximum
140 temperature in the vertical direction found between 200 and 900 metres (Shu et al., 2019) in
141 the Arctic Ocean. The Atlantic Water Core Depth (AWCD) is the depth of the AWCT. AWCT and
142 AWCD are spatially averaged 2D variables, evaluated along defined transects or regions.

143 2.2.2 Statistical tools

144 We use a set of statistical metrics to evaluate the skill of CMIP6 ensemble members in reproducing
145 observed variability in the SPG and in representing Atlantic Water properties in the Arctic.
146 Specifically, we compute the Pearson Correlation Coefficient (PCC; (Taylor, 2001)) to assess
147 the degree of linear agreement between the AMOC-SST index from model simulations and the
148 observed index derived from HadISST, over the selection period (1960–1990). This allows us to
149 identify ensemble members that exhibit realistic temporal variability in upstream ocean conditions
150 relevant to anticipate changes in the Arctic Ocean.

151 To evaluate model performance in the Arctic region, we use the Root Mean Square Error (RMSE)
152 and two of its variants: the Centered RMSE (CRMSE), that removes the mean to isolate variability
153 differences, and the Normalized RMSE (NRMSE), that scales the RMSE by the mean of the
154 observed field to facilitate interpretation across variables. These metrics are applied to the AWCT
155 and AWCD in the Eurasian Arctic Ocean over the evaluation period (1980–2014), using both
156 ORAS5 reanalysis and EN4 observational products as reference.

157 The combination of these metrics allows us to evaluate both temporal variability (via PCC) and
158 absolute biases (via RMSE, CRMSE, and NRMSE), and to assess whether the selected model
159 subset improves the representation of Atlantic Water properties compared to the full ensemble.

160 Defining p_i our predicted value at time i and our o_i observed value at time i , we have:

$$RMSE = \sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^n \frac{(p_i - o_i)^2}{n}} \quad CRMSE = \sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^n \frac{((p_i - \bar{p}) - (o_i - \bar{o}))^2}{n}} \quad NRMSE = \frac{RMSE}{\bar{o}}$$

161 2.2.3 Member Selection

162 We apply a constraint or selection on the 235 ensemble members from the 12 CMIP6 models
 163 described on Table 1. Our selection is based on an AMOC-SST index derived from SST
 164 observations (Caesar et al., 2018). This index is defined by taking the anomaly (Fig. 1, left)
 165 with respect to 1871-1900 of the difference between the global and SPG region (Fig. 1, right)
 166 November-May SST.

Figure 1. Description of the AMOC-SST index (annual values is in blue, 20 years running mean is in dark blue) as described in Caesar et al. (2018), using HadISST data. The anomaly plotted in the left is obtained by subtracting November-May SST in the SPG (blue zone in the right map) to the global November-May SST.

167 We select the model members from the CMIP6 models described in Table 1 that display an
 168 AMOC-SST index with PCC higher than 0.5 ($pval \ll 0.01$) with the AMOC-SST index based on
 169 HadISST over the period 1960-1990. In a tracer experiment (Wefing et al., 2021), it was found that
 170 it takes about 10 years for the Atlantic Water layer to reach the Nansen Basin (see their figure 6)
 171 after entering the Arctic Ocean through those 3 branches: Norwegian Coastal Current (NCC), Fram
 172 Strait Branch Water (FSBW), Barents Sea Branch Water (BSBW). Therefore, the evaluation of our
 173 selection is done at the end of the historical period (1980-2014), to allow for the water masses to
 174 travel and reach the Eurasian Arctic Ocean.

3 RESULTS

175 To assess whether the selected ensemble members offer improved performance compared to the
176 full ensemble, we evaluate the Atlantic Water Core Temperature (AWCT) and Core Depth (AWCD)
177 over the Eurasian Arctic region using RMSE, NRMSE, and PCC. These metrics allow us to
178 quantify both the magnitude of model biases and the degree to which model variability matches
179 observations and reanalysis products. The results are summarized in Table 2, which shows that the
180 selected ensemble exhibits reduced RMSE and increased correlation for both AWCT and AWCD,
181 suggesting a more realistic representation of Atlantic Water properties.

182 3.1 AW layer in Reanalysis, Observation and CMIP6 models

Figure 2. Trend of the AWCT in the ORAS5 reanalysis calculated from least squares polynomial fit over the 1970-2018 period.

183 A warming trend is found in the AW layer in last decades of the ORAS5 reanalysis (Fig. 2). This
184 finding is consistent with former studies (Richards et al., 2022; Wang et al., 2024), and emphasises
185 the importance of having a fair representation of these water masses entering the Arctic for future
186 projections. The trend reaches 2°C in the Barents Sea and Fram Strait and is found over the whole
187 Arctic Ocean, with smaller values (< 0.5°C) along the Canadian Archipelago except in front of the
188 Bering strait. The AW layer displays a cooling trend in the Canadian Basin, that could be linked to
189 a strengthening of the Beaufort Gyre (Richards et al., 2022). Uncertainty however remains large in
190 the ocean reanalyses for the Arctic Ocean: (Rautiainen, 2020) compared the temperature trends for
191 the layer [300 - 700 m] in the Arctic for several reanalyses (including ORAS5) and found some
192 disagreement between the reanalysis products.

193 In order to assess the spread in CMIP6 models regarding the representation of the AW in the
194 Arctic, we evaluate the AWCT and AWCD for 12 CMIP6 models (see section 2.1) over different

195 transects across the Arctic, following the ocean circulation of the deep waters. The top map in
196 Fig. 3(a) shows the AWCD averaged over 1979-2018 of the ORAS5 reanalysis. In this product,
197 the depth of the AW layer core is about 200 metres in the Barents Sea and over Fram Strait and
198 it reaches 500 metres in the Beaufort Sea. To capture AW flowing from the Eurasian Basin and
199 into the Amerasian Basin, the time series of the AWCT and AWCD (mean and standard deviation)
200 averaged over the transect at the entrance of the Amundsen Basin, which is the deepest abyssal
201 plain in the Arctic Ocean (red transect in Fig. 3(a)), are computed and displayed in Fig. 3(b) and
202 (c). Core depth in excess of 500 metres likely reflects limited model skill.

203 Time series in Fig. 3(b) and (c) show the CMIP6 models spread (measured as one standard
204 deviation from the ensemble mean) for the representation of the AW layer in the Arctic. The
205 full ensemble spread, calculated as the standard deviation across all ensemble members, is 0.9°C
206 over the period for the AWCT and 246 meters for the AWCD. For the AWCT the models with
207 maximum spread are E3SM-2-0 (0.9°C) and EC-Earth3 (0.36°C). The ones with minimum spread
208 are GISS-E2-1-G (0.04°C) and NorCPM1 (0.05°C). The spread in AWCD varies from 22 metres
209 for the model MIROC6 to 231 metres for the model CNRM-CM6-1.

210 In order to evaluate the CMIP6 ensemble mean bias, we estimate the AWCT and AWCD averaged
211 over 1979-2014 for the ORAS5 reanalysis and 1970-2014 for EN4 product (see Data section).
212 The results are very different for the AWCT as ORAS5 has an averaged AWCT of 0.29°C while
213 EN4 AWCT is 1.18°C . This difference of almost one degree could be explained by the fact that
214 observations are hard to obtain in this remote region with extreme conditions. The sparsity of
215 hydrographic profile measurements increases the uncertainties of the ocean subsurface data (Uotila
216 et al., 2019; Zuo et al., 2019). The reanalysis and the observations agree more on the depth of
217 the AWCT, ORAS5 has an averaged AWCD of 380 metres and EN4 average is 347 metres. From
218 specific studies (Richards et al. (2022), their Fig. 2) focusing on the AW, it seems EN4 is closer to
219 other observation products than ORAS5, looking at the area close to the transect in the Amundsen
220 Basin.

221 The multi-model mean (MMM) AWCT have a cold bias as it is 0.26°C over 1950-2014 and
222 half of the models have a AWCT lower than 0°C (ACCESS-ESM1-5, CanESM5, CNRM-CM6-1,
223 HadGEM3-GC31-LL, UKESM1-0-LL). MMM AWCD over 1950-2014 is 700 metres and almost
224 every model shows a too deep AWCT except for E3SM-2-0 (205 metres) which displays a very
225 different vertical water mass structure compared to the other CMIP6 models (see Supplementary
226 Fig. S10) and NorCPM1 (440 metres) which has the less biased AWCD.

227 AWCT and AWCD time series are provided for other regions (Barents Sea Opening or BSO,
228 Fram Strait and Makarov Basin) as Supplementary Material (Fig. S2, S3, S4). A positive trend
229 appears at the end of the historical period in the AWCT over the BSO in the multi-model ensemble
230 mean, and also EN4 and ORAS5. An assessment of the AWCT and AWCD for the model means,
231 reanalysis and observations over the 1950-1980 period for different transects over the Arctic is

Figure 3. The top map (a) shows the 1979-2014 mean of the AWCD for ORAS5 reanalysis. Times series of the AWCT (b) and AWCD (c) are averaged over the transect in the Amundsen Basin plotted in red in the top map. The thick lines represent the mean of the CMIP6 models and the envelope is the spread (one standard deviation) of the models. The thick black line is the multi-model mean (MMM). The ORAS5 reanalysis (mean and standard deviation) time series are in orange and the EN4 product is the thick red line.

232 provided in Supplementary Fig. S5 and S6. ES3M-2-0 shows the most biased mean state for the
 233 different transects considered.

234 3.2 The model member selection

235 The selection method is applied to the ensemble members over the 1960-1990 period (see the
 236 Method section) and 19 members out of 235 are selected. A Taylor diagram in Fig. 4 describes
 237 the distribution of the members in terms of correlation coefficient and centered RMSE (see 2.2

238 section). We note that the selected members based on our correlation criteria (coarse crosses) show
 239 a wide range of centered RMSE (measured by the distance to the black star). This highlights the
 240 difficulty in choosing between improving correlation or reducing bias when selecting the members.
 241 The relatively small fraction of members selected (8 %) suggest that this method could be tested on
 242 a larger dataset to identify more members that are well correlated with the AMOC-SST index.

243 To illustrate the sensitivity to the window period used for the selection, Supplementary Fig. S7
 244 shows other periods for comparison, the amount of members selected varies around 10% of the
 245 total numbers of members for the different time windows.

Figure 4. Taylor diagram showing the relative relations of the climate models members based on correlations (red segment is the 0.5 value), standard deviations, and centred RMSE (half circle, red for 0.5 value). Crosses represent the CMIP6 model ensemble members. Bold crosses are the members selected i.e. the members with $PCC > 0.5$ ($pval \ll 0.01$) w.r.t the reference: the HadISST AMOC-SST index over 1960-1990.

246 The time series of the AMOC-SST index for the ensemble mean, the selection ensemble mean,
 247 and the observations (HadISST) are presented in Fig. 5. The selection ensemble mean displays
 248 a better correlation ($PCC=0.32$) with the HadISST AMOC-SST index than the ensemble mean
 249 ($PCC=0.12$) over 1980-2014 (so after the selection period which is 1960-1990). This persistence
 250 suggests that the model members selected may have a variability closer to the observations of the
 251 surface temperature in the SPG region, for several decades after the selection is done. The method
 252 shows little sensitivity to the time window: when the selection is performed over 1950–1990, the

253 correlation for the 1980–2014 period increases from 0.12 (all members) to 0.50 (selected members)
 254 (see Supplementary Fig. S8).

Figure 5. AMOC-SST index for the multimodel ensemble mean (blue), the observations (HadISST, black) and the ensemble mean of the selection (orange). The orange window highlights the period used for the selection (1960-1990).

255 3.3 Evaluation of the members selected

256 The upstream impact of our approach is tested focusing on the representation of the AW properties
 257 at the entrance of the Eurasian Arctic Ocean (Fig. 6) over the end of the historical period [1980 -
 258 2014]. The figure 6 displays a 2D map of the AWCT of the reanalysis ORAS5 over the period 1979-
 259 2018 (entire period available), showing a cooling of the water from the Eurasian to the Canadian
 260 Basin. Equivalent figure using the EN4 product is available in the Supplementary material (Fig.
 261 S9).

262 Mean bias and correlation of AWCT and AWCD with respect to reanalysis (ORAS5) and
 263 observations (EN4) are calculated over the Eurasian Arctic region in Fig. 6 and displayed in Table
 264 2. NRMSE is used for AWCD in order to bring the RMSE between 0 and 1 and make it more
 265 readable.

266 Regarding the AWCT (Table 2, top), the selection ensemble mean is better correlated with the
 267 reanalysis ORAS5 and to the EN4 observation over the Eurasian Arctic than the total ensemble.
 268 The RMSE is reduced when estimated against ORAS5 and EN4 for the selection ensemble mean
 269 as compared to the total ensemble mean. For the AWCD (Table 2, bottom), both correlation and
 270 error are also improved, when the selection ensemble mean is compared to ORAS5 and EN4.

Figure 6. AWCT of the ORAS5 reanalysis averaged over 1979-2018. The black trapeze shows the region used for the evaluation of the ensemble selection approach.

AWCT [1980-2014]	RMSE	PCC
Ens. mean EN4	0.67 (0.23)	0.67 (pval \ll 0.01)
Selection EN4	0.57 (0.22)	0.74 (pval \ll 0.01)
Ens. mean ORAS5	0.19 (0.11)	0.58 (pval \ll 0.01)
Selection ORAS5	0.11 (0.09)	0.7 (pval \ll 0.01)

AWCD [1980-2014]	RMSE	PCC
Ens. mean EN4	0.73 (0.14)	0.49 (pval \ll 0.01)
Selection EN4	0.55 (0.13)	0.64 (pval \ll 0.01)
Ens. mean ORAS5	0.78 (0.10)	0.19 (pval = 0.26)
Selection ORAS5	0.59 (0.09)	0.45 (pval \ll 0.01)

Table 2. Evaluation of the AWCT (top) and AWCD (bottom) over the period 1980-2014, total and selection ensemble mean (based on the 1960-1990 period) are compared to a reanalysis product (ORAS5) and observations (EN4) in terms of bias (RMSE for AWCT, and NRMSE for AWCD) and correlation (PCC). CRMSE is in parenthesis.

271 Equivalent results are provided in the Supplementary material for another selection period (1950-
 272 1990, see Table S1), to illustrate the sensitivity of the results. Several other periods were tested
 273 (not shown), and resulted in a systematic reduction of the RMSE and increase of correlation with
 274 respect to reanalysis and observation for both AWCT and AWCD, with the exception that for some
 275 selection periods (including 1950-1990) where the AWCT RMSE with respect to ORAS5 was
 276 higher for the selected members. In those cases, the AW layer from the selection remains more
 277 shallow (AWCD is less biased) but displays a colder AWCT than the total (original) ensemble
 278 mean (see Supplementary Fig. S10).

Figure 7. Time series of the AWCT (a) and the AWCD (b) averaged over the region in Fig.6 for the multi-model ensemble (members in grey, mean in black as MMM) and the selected ensemble mean (blue for selection with $PCC > 0.5$, green for $PCC > 0.65$, selection is done over 1960-1990), ORAS5 reanalysis (red) and observations (orange). Figure (c) shows the temperature profiles averaged over 1980-2014 of the ensemble members, selected members are plotted with thicker lines.

279 Time series of the individual CMIP6 ensemble members are represented in Fig. 7 for the AWCT
 280 (Fig. 7a) and the AWCD (Fig. 7b), together with the reanalysis and the observations, and averaged
 281 over the black trapeze in Fig. 6 which mainly corresponds to the Amundsen and the Nansen Basins.

282 The ensemble mean of the members with a significant correlation of 0.5 or higher (blue line) has
 283 a warmer AWCT, in better agreement with ORAS5 and EN4. Selecting the members showing a

284 correlation coefficient of 0.65 or higher (green line) places the selection ensemble between the
285 EN4 and ORAS5 estimates, making it difficult to assess if the subselection is more or less biased.
286 Some studies suggest that EN4 may provide a more realistic representation, while ORAS5 might
287 be too cold for the AWCT (Uotila et al., 2019; Richards et al., 2022), indicating that our selection
288 constitutes an improvement. After 2007, the AWCT for ORAS5, the ensemble mean and both
289 selection ensemble means become hardly distinguishable.

290 Regarding the AWCD, the selection performs better for the AWCD for the whole period compared
291 to both observations and reanalysis, especially in the decades after the selection. Increasing the
292 threshold for the selection from 0.5 to 0.65 for the correlation coefficient reduces the bias of
293 the selected ensemble. The variability is also better captured, and the evaluation is easier as
294 observations and reanalysis are much closer over this region for the estimation of the AWCD.

295 The temperature profile over 1980-2014 of the ensemble members are compared to ORAS5 and
296 EN4 for the same region (Fig. 7c). Most members display a too deep core temperature below
297 200 meters, a well known bias in CMIP models (Langehaug et al. (2023); Shu et al. (2019), and
298 see Introduction, 1). The MIROC6 model has warmer temperatures than observations below 300
299 metres, up to a difference of 1.5°C at 1000 metres depth. E3SM-2-0 displays a different structure,
300 possibly because of the unstructured grid mesh used in the ocean for this model.

4 DISCUSSION

301 We have applied a selection method based on an AMOC-SST index to 235 historical simulations
302 from 12 CMIP6 models. The selection of members is in closer agreement with the observed
303 index than the total ensemble mean in the SPG over the next 25 years after the selection period
304 showing that we were able to constrain the internal variability of the model ensemble members.
305 The selection also displays over the latter period a reduced error and a better correlation for both
306 AWCT and AWCD in the Eurasian Arctic when compared to reanalysis and observations.

307 While CMIP6 models are known to underestimate ocean heat transport into the Arctic, our
308 selection method does not explicitly correct this bias. However, the improved representation of
309 Atlantic Water properties (AWCT and AWCD) in the selected ensemble suggests that the method
310 goes beyond simply matching historical trends in the SPG.

311 The selection based on the AMOC-SST index leads to consistent improvements in both mean
312 state and variability in downstream Arctic regions over an independent evaluation period. This
313 indicates that the selected members likely capture more realistic large-scale drivers of Arctic
314 Atlantification, rather than coincidentally aligning with observed past variability. This is consistent
315 with the understanding that AMOC plays a central role in driving multidecadal variability in the
316 North Atlantic, including SST and salinity patterns that influence Arctic Ocean properties Zhang
317 et al. (2019).

318 We have shown that the Atlantic Water layer in the selected ensemble consistently remains
319 shallower and, thus, more realistic, across various selection periods. However, increasing the
320 constraint—by selecting members with a PCC greater than 0.65 instead of 0.5—leads to a
321 significant reduction in the number of selected members. Most members in the total ensemble
322 exhibit a low PCC (< 0.5) with the AMOC-SST index, indicating that this method would benefit
323 from being tested with a larger ensemble size to enhance its robustness.

324 The correlation threshold ($\text{PCC} > 0.5$, $p \ll 0.01$) used for ensemble member selection was
325 chosen to ensure a statistically meaningful relationship with the observed AMOC-SST index while
326 preserving enough members for further evaluation. Although this value is somewhat arbitrary, it
327 reflects a moderate level of correlation commonly accepted in climate model evaluation. To test
328 the sensitivity of the results, we explored alternative thresholds (e.g., $\text{PCC} > 0.65$), which led to
329 fewer selected members but showed similar improvements in downstream variables (see Fig. 7 and
330 Supplementary Fig. S10). In future work, this selection approach could be expanded to include
331 additional metrics—such as RMSE or trend agreement in key Arctic variables—to develop a more
332 comprehensive and physically grounded ensemble selection.

333 One limitation of the current approach is the relatively small number of ensemble members
334 retained after selection: only 19 out of 235 (8%). This strict filtering was required to ensure
335 statistical significance ($\text{PCC} > 0.5$, $p \ll 0.01$) and relevance to observed AMOC-SST variability,
336 but it does reduce the robustness of the selected ensemble and raises the possibility of overfitting to
337 historical trends. This could limit the generalizability of the results, especially for future projections
338 beyond the training window.

339 While the selected members consistently show improved performance in downstream variables
340 (AWCT and AWCD), we consider this study a first step toward a scalable method. Future work
341 should focus on expanding the ensemble size, applying multi-metric selection, or adopting
342 ensemble weighting schemes. These approaches could preserve more diversity within the ensemble
343 while still leveraging observed constraints to improve model skill in the Arctic.

344 An important consideration in this study is the use of two different reference datasets—ORAS5
345 reanalysis and EN4 observational product—for evaluating Atlantic Water properties. Unlike
346 purely observational datasets like EN4 which exhibit low bias in the mean state, ORAS5 uses an
347 ensemble-based data assimilation approach, maintaining physical consistency in ocean circulation
348 and stratification Carton et al. (2019). These datasets produce notable differences for the Atlantic
349 Water Core Temperature (AWCT) in the Arctic. This highlights the inherent uncertainty in Arctic
350 subsurface observations and reanalysis products, driven by limited *in situ* measurements and the
351 use of extrapolation techniques in regions with insufficient data coverage. While these uncertainties
352 complicate direct model evaluation, our selection method demonstrates consistent improvement
353 in representing Atlantic Water Core Depth (AWCD) and, in most cases, AWCT relative to both
354 ORAS5 and EN4. The agreement across multiple reference datasets suggests that the benefits of
355 the selection are robust to the choice of validation product. Nonetheless, we acknowledge that

356 observational uncertainty remains a key limitation in constraining model skill in the Arctic and
357 should be accounted for in future multi-dataset evaluations.

358 The selection method in this study relies on the AMOC-SST index, that is derived from SPG
359 SST anomalies and has been proposed as an observational proxy for AMOC variability (Caesar
360 et al., 2018). This approach is motivated by evidence that SPG surface temperature variability is
361 associated with broader Atlantic circulation changes that influence heat transport into the Arctic
362 (e.g., Fan et al. (2023); Drews et al. (2024)). However, we acknowledge that this index alone does
363 not fully capture the complexity of the mechanisms involved in Arctic Atlantification. Processes
364 such as salinity-driven stratification, vertical mixing, and gyre dynamics are also key contributors
365 to Atlantic Water transport.

366 The AMOC-SST index serves here as a statistical constraint, reflecting upstream variability
367 patterns linked to Arctic subsurface changes. While our results suggest this approach leads to
368 improved agreement with observations for AW core temperature and depth, we recognize that
369 future ensemble selection efforts could benefit from integrating multiple physical metrics—such
370 as OHT estimates, salinity structure, or circulation strength—to build a more mechanistic and
371 comprehensive framework.

372 Although this study focuses on the connection between SPG surface temperature multidecadal
373 variability and Arctic Atlantification, we acknowledge that multiple mechanisms contribute to
374 observed Arctic warming. For instance, the North Atlantic Oscillation (NAO) influences both
375 ocean and atmospheric circulation patterns, modulating heat and freshwater transport into the
376 Arctic. Sea ice loss itself acts as both a symptom and amplifier of warming through ice–albedo
377 feedbacks and changes in vertical heat fluxes. In addition, atmospheric heat transport and changes
378 in wind-driven ocean circulation have been shown to play key roles in shaping Arctic temperature
379 trends and variability.

380 The AMOC-SST index used here captures part of the decadal-scale oceanic variability linked
381 to AMOC, but it does not encompass all relevant feedbacks or processes. Our results should
382 therefore be interpreted as highlighting one influential pathway, rather than a comprehensive causal
383 mechanism. Future ensemble selection frameworks could benefit from incorporating multiple
384 observational constraints — including sea ice metrics, surface heat fluxes, and freshwater content
385 — to better represent the interconnected drivers of Arctic change.

5 CONCLUSION

386 In conclusion, our study using CMIP6 climate models suggests that the link between the surface
387 SPG and the Arctic region, the Arctic-Atlantic connectivity, is of first order importance for
388 improving the representation of the Atlantic layer of the Arctic Ocean. While our findings provide a
389 foundation for further investigation, the complex nature of these interactions highlight the need for
390 additional research to clarify the extent and mechanisms of this relationship. Continued exploration

391 in this area will be essential for enhancing our understanding of the Atlantic Water layer and its
392 broader implications.

393 The next step in this work would involve increasing the number of CMIP6 historical simulations
394 to provide predictions with superior skill for the arctic region based on the ensemble screening
395 approach and to enhance the robustness of the method for more models. As a perspective regarding
396 the evaluation method, the selection process could be assessed in additional regions along the
397 Arctic circulation pathways. More complex selection methods might also be explored, such
398 as employing a weighted ensemble mean that incorporates weights based on trends and mean
399 states of the AMOC-SST index, as well as AWCT and AWCD in the Fram Strait and at the
400 Barents Sea Opening. Additionally, incorporating more in-situ observations from the Arctic Data
401 Centre (<https://arcticdata.io/catalog/>) could enhance the evaluation, tailored to
402 the specific regions being studied.

403 Beyond ensemble selection, improving the representation of Atlantic Water in the Arctic also
404 requires advances in model physics. Current CMIP6 models often lack the spatial resolution to
405 capture key ocean processes, such as narrow boundary currents, mesoscale eddies, and interactions
406 with complex Arctic bathymetry. These limitations contribute to biases in the depth, temperature,
407 and transport of Atlantic Water. Higher-resolution ocean components, better vertical mixing
408 schemes, and improved treatment of overflow processes at key gateways (e.g., Fram Strait, Barents
409 Sea Opening) are essential steps forward.

410 In addition, better coupling between ocean, sea ice, and atmospheric processes — particularly in
411 the North Atlantic and Nordic Seas — would help models simulate more realistic pathways and
412 feedbacks. We recommend that future CMIP phases continue developing eddy-permitting models
413 and explore hybrid approaches that combine dynamical refinement with data-driven constraints.
414 Together, these efforts could enhance both the fidelity of model outputs and the utility of ensemble
415 screening methods such as the one presented here.

DATA AVAILABILITY STATEMENT

416 CMIP6 data is available through the Earth System Grid Federation (ESGF) website <https://esgf-node.llnl.gov/search/cmip6/>. Source code, post-processing scripts, data
417 and materials are available on request.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

424 The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial
425 relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

REFERENCES

- 426 Andrews, M. B., Ridley, J. K., Wood, R. A., Andrews, T., Blockley, E. W., Booth, B., et al. (2020).
427 Historical Simulations With HadGEM3-GC3.1 for CMIP6. *Journal of Advances in Modeling*
428 *Earth Systems* 12. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1029/2019MS001995>
- 429 Årthun, M., Eldevik, T., Smedsrud, L. H., Skagseth, Ø., and Ingvaldsen, R. B. (2012). Quantifying
430 the Influence of Atlantic Heat on Barents Sea Ice Variability and Retreat. *Journal of Climate* 25,
431 4736 – 4743. doi:10.1175/JCLI-D-11-00466.1
- 432 Årthun, M., Eldevik, T., Viste, E., Drange, H., Furevik, T., Johnson, H. L., et al. (2017). Skillful
433 prediction of northern climate provided by the ocean. *Nature Communications* 8, 15875.
434 doi:10.1038/ncomms15875
- 435 Barton, B. I., Lenn, Y.-D., and Lique, C. (2018). Observed Atlantification of the Barents Sea Causes
436 the Polar Front to Limit the Expansion of Winter Sea Ice. *Journal of Physical Oceanography* 48,
437 1849 – 1866. doi:10.1175/JPO-D-18-0003.1
- 438 Bethke, I., Wang, Y., Counillon, F., Keenlyside, N., Kimmritz, M., Fransner, F., et al. (2021).
439 NorCPM1 and its contribution to CMIP6 DCP. *Geoscientific Model Development* 14, 7073–
440 7116. doi:10.5194/gmd-14-7073-2021
- 441 Bonnet, R., Swingedouw, D., Gastineau, G., Boucher, O., Deshayes, J., Hourdin, F., et al.
442 (2021). Increased risk of near term global warming due to a recent AMOC weakening. *Nature*
443 *Communications* 12, 6108. doi:10.1038/s41467-021-26370-0
- 444 Boucher, O., Servonnat, J., Albright, A. L., Aumont, O., Balkanski, Y., Bastrikov, V., et al. (2020).
445 Presentation and Evaluation of the IPSL-CM6A-LR Climate Model. *Journal of Advances in*
446 *Modeling Earth Systems* 12, e2019MS002010. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1029/2019MS002010>
- 447 Caesar, L., Rahmstorf, S., Robinson, A., Feulner, G., and Saba, V. (2018). Observed fingerprint
448 of a weakening Atlantic Ocean overturning circulation. *Nature* 556, 191–196. doi:10.1038/
449 s41586-018-0006-5
- 450 Carton, J. A., Penny, S. G., and Kalnay, E. (2019). Temperature and salinity variability in the
451 soda3, ecco4r3, and oras5 ocean reanalyses, 1993–2015. *Journal of Climate* 32, 2277 – 2293.
452 doi:10.1175/JCLI-D-18-0605.1
- 453 Copernicus (2021). ORAS5 global ocean reanalysis monthly data from 1958 to present. *Copernicus*
454 *Climate Change Service (C3S) Climate Data Store (CDS)* 10
- 455 Couldrey, M. P., Gregory, J. M., Boeira Dias, F., Dobrohotoff, P., Domingues, C. M., Garuba,
456 O., et al. (2021). What causes the spread of model projections of ocean dynamic sea-level
457 change in response to greenhouse gas forcing? *Climate Dynamics* 56, 155–187. doi:10.1007/
458 s00382-020-05471-4

- 459 Deser, C., Lehner, F., Rodgers, K. B., Ault, T., Delworth, T. L., DiNezio, P. N., et al. (2020).
460 Insights from Earth system model initial-condition large ensembles and future prospects. *Nature*
461 *Climate Change* 10, 277–286. doi:10.1038/s41558-020-0731-2
- 462 Docquier, D. and Koenigk, T. (2021). Observation-based selection of climate models projects
463 Arctic ice-free summers around 2035. *Communications Earth & Environment* 2, 144. doi:10.
464 1038/s43247-021-00214-7
- 465 Döscher, R., Acosta, M., Alessandri, A., Anthoni, P., Arsouze, T., Bergman, T., et al. (2022). The
466 EC-Earth3 Earth system model for the Coupled Model Intercomparison Project 6. *Geoscientific*
467 *Model Development* 15, 2973–3020. doi:10.5194/gmd-15-2973-2022
- 468 Drews, A., Schmith, T., Tian, T., Wang, Y., Devilliers, M., Keenlyside, N. S., et al. (2024).
469 The Crucial Role of the Subpolar North Atlantic for Skillful Decadal Climate Predictions.
470 *Geophysical Research Letters* 51, e2024GL109415. doi:https://doi.org/10.1029/2024GL109415
- 471 Eyring, V., Bony, S., Meehl, G. A., Senior, C. A., Stevens, B., Stouffer, R. J., et al. (2016).
472 Overview of the coupled model intercomparison project phase 6 (cmip6) experimental design and
473 organization. *Geoscientific Model Development* 9, 1937–1958. doi:10.5194/gmd-9-1937-2016
- 474 Fan, H., Borchert, L. F., Brune, S., Koul, V., and Baehr, J. (2023). North Atlantic subpolar
475 gyre provides downstream ocean predictability. *npj Climate and Atmospheric Science* 6, 145.
476 doi:10.1038/s41612-023-00469-1
- 477 Garuba, O. A. and Klinger, B. A. (2016). Ocean Heat Uptake and Interbasin Transport of the
478 Passive and Redistributive Components of Surface Heating. *Journal of Climate* 29, 7507 – 7527.
479 doi:10.1175/JCLI-D-16-0138.1
- 480 Gervais, M., Shaman, J., and Kushnir, Y. (2018). Mechanisms Governing the Development of the
481 North Atlantic Warming Hole in the CESM-LE Future Climate Simulations. *Journal of Climate*
482 31, 5927 – 5946. doi:10.1175/JCLI-D-17-0635.1
- 483 Golaz, J.-C., Van Roekel, L. P., Zheng, X., Roberts, A. F., Wolfe, J. D., Lin, W., et al. (2022). The
484 DOE E3SM Model Version 2: Overview of the Physical Model and Initial Model Evaluation.
485 *Journal of Advances in Modeling Earth Systems* 14. doi:https://doi.org/10.1029/2022MS003156
- 486 Good, S. A., Martin, M. J., and Rayner, N. A. (2013). EN4: Quality controlled ocean temperature
487 and salinity profiles and monthly objective analyses with uncertainty estimates. *Journal of*
488 *Geophysical Research: Oceans* 118, 6704–6716. doi:10.1002/2013JC009067
- 489 Goosse, H., Kay, J. E., Armour, K. C., Bodas-Salcedo, A., Chepfer, H., Docquier, D., et al. (2018).
490 Quantifying climate feedbacks in polar regions. *Nature Communications* 9, 1919
- 491 Gregory, J. M., Bouttes-Mauhourat, N., Griffies, S. M., Haak, H., Hurlin, W. J., Jungclaus, J.,
492 et al. (2016). The Flux-Anomaly-Forced Model Intercomparison Project (FAFMIP) contribution
493 to CMIP6: Investigation of sea-level and ocean climate change in response to CO2 forcing.
494 *Geoscientific Model Development* 9, 3993–4017. doi:10.5194/gmd-9-3993-2016
- 495 Hansen, B., Larsen, K. M. H., Hátún, H., Olsen, S. M., Gierisch, A. M. U., Østerhus, S., et al.
496 (2023). The iceland-faroe warm-water flow towards the arctic estimated from satellite altimetry
497 and in situ observations. *EGUsphere* 2023, 1–42. doi:10.5194/egusphere-2023-828

- 498 Hattermann, T., Isachsen, P. E., von Appen, W.-J., Albretsen, J., and Sundfjord, A. (2016). Eddy-
499 driven recirculation of atlantic water in fram strait. *Geophysical Research Letters* 43, 3406–3414.
500 doi:<https://doi.org/10.1002/2016GL068323>
- 501 He, C., Clement, A. C., Cane, M. A., Murphy, L. N., Klavans, J. M., and Fenske, T. M.
502 (2022). A north atlantic warming hole without ocean circulation. *Geophysical Research*
503 *Letters* 49, e2022GL100420. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1029/2022GL100420>. E2022GL100420
504 2022GL100420
- 505 Heuzé, C., Zanowski, H., Karam, S., and Muilwijk, M. (2023). The Deep Arctic Ocean and Fram
506 Strait in CMIP6 Models. *Journal of Climate* 36, 2551 – 2584. doi:10.1175/JCLI-D-22-0194.1
- 507 Hwang, Y.-T., Frierson, D. M. W., and Kay, J. E. (2011). Coupling between Arctic feedbacks and
508 changes in poleward energy transport. *Geophysical Research Letters* 38. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1029/2011GL048546>
- 510 IPCC (2023). *Ocean, Cryosphere and Sea Level Change* (Cambridge University Press), chap. 9.
511 1211–1362
- 512 Jungclaus, J. H., Lohmann, K., and Zanchettin, D. (2014). Enhanced 20th-century heat transfer to
513 the Arctic simulated in the context of climate variations over the last millennium. *Climate of the*
514 *Past* 10, 2201–2213. doi:10.5194/cp-10-2201-2014
- 515 Keil, P., Mauritsen, T., Jungclaus, J., Hedemann, C., Olonscheck, D., and Ghosh, R. (2020).
516 Multiple drivers of the north atlantic warming hole. *Nature Climate Change* 10, 667–671.
517 doi:10.1038/s41558-020-0819-8
- 518 Kelley, M., Schmidt, G. A., Nazarenko, L. S., Bauer, S. E., Ruedy, R., Russell, G. L., et al. (2020).
519 GISS-E2.1: Configurations and Climatology. *Journal of Advances in Modeling Earth Systems*
520 12, e2019MS002025. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1029/2019MS002025>
- 521 Khosravi, N., Wang, Q., Koldunov, N., Hinrichs, C., Semmler, T., Danilov, S., et al. (2022). The
522 Arctic Ocean in CMIP6 Models: Biases and Projected Changes in Temperature and Salinity.
523 *Earth's Future* 10, e2021EF002282. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1029/2021EF002282>
- 524 Koenigk, T. and Brodeau, L. (2014). Ocean heat transport into the Arctic in the twentieth
525 and twenty-first century in EC-Earth. *Climate Dynamics* 42, 3101–3120. doi:10.1007/
526 s00382-013-1821-x
- 527 Langehaug, H. R., Sagen, H., Stallemo, A., Uotila, P., Rautiainen, L., Olsen, S. M., et al. (2023).
528 Constraining cmip6 estimates of arctic ocean temperature and salinity in 2025-2055. *Frontiers*
529 *in Marine Science* 10. doi:10.3389/fmars.2023.1211562
- 530 Le Bras, P., Sévellec, F., Tandeo, P., Ruiz, J., and Ailliot, P. (2024). Selecting and weighting
531 dynamical models using data-driven approaches. *Nonlinear Processes in Geophysics* 31, 303–
532 317. doi:10.5194/npg-31-303-2024
- 533 Madonna, E. and Sandø, A. B. (2022). Understanding Differences in North Atlantic Poleward
534 Ocean Heat Transport and Its Variability in Global Climate Models. *Geophysical Research*
535 *Letters* 49. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1029/2021GL096683>

- 536 Mankin, J. S., Lehner, F., Coats, S., and McKinnon, K. A. (2020). The Value of Initial Condition
537 Large Ensembles to Robust Adaptation Decision-Making. *Earth's Future* 8. doi:[https://doi.org/](https://doi.org/10.1029/2020EF001610)
538 10.1029/2020EF001610
- 539 Maslowski, W., Marble, D., Walczowski, W., Schauer, U., Clement, J. L., and Semtner, A. J.
540 (2004). On climatological mass, heat, and salt transports through the Barents Sea and Fram
541 Strait from a pan-Arctic coupled ice-ocean. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Oceans* 109.
542 doi:<https://doi.org/10.1029/2001JC001039>
- 543 Mauritsen, T., Bader, J., Becker, T., Behrens, J., Bittner, M., Brokopf, R., et al. (2019).
544 Developments in the MPI-M Earth System Model version 1.2 (MPI-ESM1.2) and Its Response
545 to Increasing CO₂. *Journal of Advances in Modeling Earth Systems* 11, 998–1038. doi:[https://](https://doi.org/10.1029/2018MS001400)
546 doi.org/10.1029/2018MS001400
- 547 Meccia, V. L., Fuentes-Franco, R., Davini, P., Bellomo, K., Fabiano, F., Yang, S., et al. (2023).
548 Internal multi-centennial variability of the Atlantic Meridional Overturning Circulation simulated
549 by EC-Earth3. *Climate Dynamics* 60, 3695–3712. doi:[10.1007/s00382-022-06534-4](https://doi.org/10.1007/s00382-022-06534-4)
- 550 Muilwijk, M., Nummelin, A., Heuzé, C., Polyakov, I. V., Zanowski, H., and Smedsrud, L. H.
551 (2023). Divergence in Climate Model Projections of Future Arctic Atlantification. *Journal of*
552 *Climate* 36, 1727 – 1748. doi:[10.1175/JCLI-D-22-0349.1](https://doi.org/10.1175/JCLI-D-22-0349.1)
- 553 Nummelin, A., Li, C., and Hezel, P. J. (2017). Connecting ocean heat transport changes from
554 the midlatitudes to the Arctic Ocean. *Geophysical Research Letters* 44, 1899–1908. doi:[https://](https://doi.org/10.1002/2016GL071333)
555 doi.org/10.1002/2016GL071333
- 556 Oldenburg, D., Armour, K. C., Thompson, L., and Bitz, C. M. (2018). Distinct Mechanisms
557 of Ocean Heat Transport Into the Arctic Under Internal Variability and Climate Change.
558 *Geophysical Research Letters* 45, 7692–7700. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1029/2018GL078719>
- 559 Orvik, K. A. and Niiler, P. (2002). Major pathways of Atlantic water in the northern North
560 Atlantic and Nordic Seas toward Arctic. *Geophysical Research Letters* 29, 2–1–2–4. doi:[https://](https://doi.org/10.1029/2002GL015002)
561 doi.org/10.1029/2002GL015002
- 562 Pan, R., Shu, Q., Wang, Q., Wang, S., Song, Z., He, Y., et al. (2023). Future Arctic Climate Change
563 in CMIP6 Strikingly Intensified by NEMO-Family Climate Models. *Geophysical Research*
564 *Letters* 50, e2022GL102077. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1029/2022GL102077>. E2022GL102077
565 2022GL102077
- 566 Pithan, F. and Mauritsen, T. (2014). Arctic amplification dominated by temperature feedbacks in
567 contemporary climate models. *Nature Geoscience* 7, 181–184
- 568 Polyakov, I. V., Ingvaldsen, R. B., Pnyushkov, A. V., Bhatt, U. S., Francis, J. A., Janout, M., et al.
569 (2023). Fluctuating Atlantic inflows modulate Arctic atlantification. *Science* 381, 972–979.
570 doi:[10.1126/science.adh5158](https://doi.org/10.1126/science.adh5158)
- 571 Polyakov, I. V., Pnyushkov, A. V., and Timokhov, L. A. (2012). Warming of the Intermediate
572 Atlantic Water of the Arctic Ocean in the 2000s. *Journal of Climate* 25, 8362 – 8370. doi:[10.](https://doi.org/10.1175/JCLI-D-12-00266.1)
573 [1175/JCLI-D-12-00266.1](https://doi.org/10.1175/JCLI-D-12-00266.1)

- 574 Rantanen, M., Karpechko, A. Y., Lipponen, A., Nordling, K., Hyvärinen, O., Ruosteenoja, K.,
575 et al. (2022). The Arctic has warmed nearly four times faster than the globe since 1979.
576 *Communications Earth & Environment* 3. doi:10.1038/s43247-022-00498-3
- 577 [Dataset] Rautiainen, L. (2020). Observed changes in the hydrography of the arctic ocean
578 Rayner, N. A., Parker, D. E., Horton, E. B., Folland, C. K., Alexander, L. V., Rowell, D. P., et al.
579 (2003). Global analyses of sea surface temperature, sea ice, and night marine air temperature
580 since the late nineteenth century. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Atmospheres* 108. doi:https://doi.org/10.1029/2002JD002670
- 582 Ribes, A., Qasmi, S., and Gillett, N. P. (2021). Making climate projections conditional on historical
583 observations. *Science Advances* 7, eabc0671. doi:10.1126/sciadv.abc0671
- 584 Richards, A. E., Johnson, H. L., and Lique, C. (2022). Spatial and temporal variability of atlantic
585 water in the arctic from 40 years of observations. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Oceans* 127,
586 e2021JC018358. doi:https://doi.org/10.1029/2021JC018358
- 587 Ruiz, J., Ailliot, P., Chau, T. T. T., Le Bras, P., Monbet, V., Sévellec, F., et al. (2022). Analog
588 data assimilation for the selection of suitable general circulation models. *Geoscientific Model
589 Development* 15, 7203–7220. doi:10.5194/gmd-15-7203-2022
- 590 Saba, V. S., Griffies, S. M., Anderson, W. G., Winton, M., Alexander, M. A., Delworth, T. L., et al.
591 (2016). Enhanced warming of the Northwest Atlantic Ocean under climate change. *Journal of
592 Geophysical Research: Oceans* 121, 118–132. doi:https://doi.org/10.1002/2015JC011346
- 593 Sellar, A. A., Jones, C. G., Mulcahy, J. P., Tang, Y., Yool, A., Wiltshire, A., et al. (2019). UKESM1:
594 Description and Evaluation of the U.K. Earth System Model. *Journal of Advances in Modeling
595 Earth Systems* 11, 4513–4558. doi:https://doi.org/10.1029/2019MS001739
- 596 Serreze, M. C. and Barry, R. G. (2011). Processes and impacts of Arctic amplification: A research
597 synthesis. *Global and Planetary Change* 77, 85–96. doi:https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gloplacha.
598 2011.03.004
- 599 Sgubin, G., Swingedouw, D., Drijfhout, S., Mary, Y., and Bennabi, A. (2017). Abrupt cooling over
600 the North Atlantic in modern climate models. *Nature Communications* 8, 14375. doi:10.1038/
601 ncomms14375
- 602 Shu, Q., Wang, Q., Su, J., Li, X., and Qiao, F. (2019). Assessment of the Atlantic water
603 layer in the Arctic Ocean in CMIP5 climate models. *Climate Dynamics* 53, 5279–5291.
604 doi:10.1007/s00382-019-04870-6
- 605 Swart, N. C., Cole, J. N. S., Kharin, V. V., Lazare, M., Scinocca, J. F., Gillett, N. P., et al. (2019).
606 The Canadian Earth System Model version 5 (CanESM5.0.3). *Geoscientific Model Development*
607 12, 4823–4873. doi:10.5194/gmd-12-4823-2019
- 608 Tatebe, H., Ogura, T., Nitta, T., Komuro, Y., Ogochi, K., Takemura, T., et al. (2019). Description
609 and basic evaluation of simulated mean state, internal variability, and climate sensitivity in
610 MIROC6. *Geoscientific Model Development* 12, 2727–2765. doi:10.5194/gmd-12-2727-2019
- 611 Taylor, K. E. (2001). Summarizing multiple aspects of model performance in a single diagram.
612 *Journal of Geophysical Research: Atmospheres* 106, 7183–7192. doi:10.1029/2000JD900719

- 613 Tokarska, K. B., Stolpe, M. B., Sippel, S., Fischer, E. M., Smith, C. J., Lehner, F., et al. (2020).
614 Past warming trend constrains future warming in CMIP6 models. *Science Advances* 6, eaaz9549.
615 doi:10.1126/sciadv.aaz9549
- 616 Tsubouchi, T., Våge, K., Hansen, B., Larsen, K. M. H., Østerhus, S., Johnson, C., et al. (2021).
617 Increased ocean heat transport into the Nordic Seas and Arctic Ocean over the period 1993–2016.
618 *Nature Climate Change* 11, 21–26. doi:10.1038/s41558-020-00941-3
- 619 Uotila, P., Goosse, H., Haines, K., Chevallier, M., Barthélemy, A., Bricaud, C., et al. (2019). An
620 assessment of ten ocean reanalyses in the polar regions. *Climate Dynamics* 52, 1613–1650.
621 doi:10.1007/s00382-018-4242-z
- 622 van der Linden, E. C., Le Bars, D., Bintanja, R., and Hazeleger, W. (2019). Oceanic heat
623 transport into the Arctic under high and low CO₂ forcing. *Climate Dynamics* 53, 4763–4780.
624 doi:10.1007/s00382-019-04824-y
- 625 Voldoire, A., Saint-Martin, D., Sénési, S., Decharme, B., Alias, A., Chevallier, M., et al. (2019).
626 Evaluation of CMIP6 DECK Experiments With CNRM-CM6-1. *Journal of Advances in*
627 *Modeling Earth Systems* 11, 2177–2213. doi:https://doi.org/10.1029/2019MS001683
- 628 Wang, Q., Shu, Q., Bozec, A., Chassignet, E. P., Fogli, P. G., Fox-Kemper, B., et al. (2024).
629 Impact of increased resolution on Arctic Ocean simulations in Ocean Model Intercomparison
630 Project phase 2 (OMIP-2). *Geoscientific Model Development* 17, 347–379. doi:10.5194/
631 gmd-17-347-2024
- 632 Wang, Q., Wekerle, C., Wang, X., Danilov, S., Koldunov, N., Sein, D., et al. (2020). Intensification
633 of the Atlantic Water Supply to the Arctic Ocean Through Fram Strait Induced by Arctic Sea
634 Ice Decline. *Geophysical Research Letters* 47, e2019GL086682. doi:https://doi.org/10.1029/
635 2019GL086682. E2019GL086682 10.1029/2019GL086682
- 636 Wefing, A.-M., Casacuberta, N., Christl, M., Gruber, N., and Smith, J. N. (2021). Circulation
637 timescales of atlantic water in the arctic ocean determined from anthropogenic radionuclides.
638 *Ocean Science* 17, 111–129. doi:10.5194/os-17-111-2021
- 639 Weijer, W., Cheng, W., Garuba, O. A., Hu, A., and Nadiga, B. T. (2020). CMIP6 Models
640 Predict Significant 21st Century Decline of the Atlantic Meridional Overturning Circulation.
641 *Geophysical Research Letters* 47, e2019GL086075. doi:https://doi.org/10.1029/2019GL086075.
642 E2019GL086075 10.1029/2019GL086075
- 643 Weijer, W., Haine, T. W., Siddiqui, A. H., Cheng, W., Veneziani, M., and Kurtakoti, P.
644 (2022). Interactions between the Arctic Mediterranean and the Atlantic Meridional Overturning
645 Circulation: A Review. *Oceanography*
- 646 Winkelbauer, S., Mayer, M., and Haimberger, L. (2024). Validation of key Arctic energy
647 and water budget components in CMIP6. *Climate Dynamics* 62, 3891–3926. doi:10.1007/
648 s00382-024-07105-5
- 649 Zhang, R., Sutton, R., Danabasoglu, G., Kwon, Y.-O., Marsh, R., Yeager, S. G., et al. (2019).
650 A review of the role of the atlantic meridional overturning circulation in atlantic multidecadal

- 651 variability and associated climate impacts. *Reviews of Geophysics* 57, 316–375. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1029/2019RG000644>
- 652
- 653 Ziehn, T., Chamberlain, M. A., Law, R. M., Lenton, A., Bodman, R. W., Dix, M., et al. (2020).
- 654 The Australian Earth System Model: ACCESS-ESM1.5. *Journal of Southern Hemisphere Earth*
- 655 *Systems Science* 70, 193–214. doi:10.1071/ES19035
- 656 Zuo, H., Balmaseda, M. A., Tietsche, S., Mogensen, K., and Mayer, M. (2019). The ECMWF
- 657 operational ensemble reanalysis–analysis system for ocean and sea ice: a description of the
- 658 system and assessment. *Ocean Science* 15, 779–808. doi:10.5194/os-15-779-2019